

FRACTIONAL ORDER ITERATIVE LEARNING CONTROLLER WITH PSO-BASED PARAMETERS TUNING FOR ROBOTIC SYSTEMS

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Abstract: *This research investigates the improvement of trajectory tracking in robotic systems by employing a model-based controller and a fractional-order iterative learning controller (FOILC). Robotic systems are subject to high uncertainty in the mathematical model, which directly impacts the quality of the model-based control strategy. This study focuses on parametric uncertainty in the robot model. The proposed solution capitalizes on the synergies between model-based control and fractional-order iterative learning strategy. FOILC controller's task is to mitigate the influence uncertainty has on trajectory tracking iteratively. Central to this investigation is the tuning of control parameters, a task undertaken by utilizing the Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) algorithm. By leveraging PSO, the FOILC control parameters are optimized to maximize the system's performance by reducing the trajectory tracking error according to the chosen objective function. The efficiency of the proposed control algorithms is evaluated through extensive simulation on a three degree of freedom robot arm. The findings underscore the performance improvement of the tuned fractional-order iterative learning controller over its integer-order counterpart in trajectory tracking. These results not only validate the efficiency of the FOILC approach but also highlight the significance of fine parameter tuning methodologies in advancing the capabilities of robotic systems based on the dynamics model.*

Keywords: *Iterative learning control, robotics, fractional calculus, parameter tuning.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Trajectory tracking is one of the main problems in robotics, where the goal is to control a robot's motion to follow a desired trajectory. The desired trajectory is usually defined in operational space using Cartesian coordinates, representing the position and orientation of the robot's end-effector. Trajectory tracking can be a complex problem from the control design standpoint, especially when parametric uncertainties, unmodeled dynamics, or other uncertainties are present in the system. Uncertainty needs to be addressed to make the system's performance satisfactory. Robot manipulators are usually designated with repetitive tasks such as welding, assembly, sorting, etc. Iterative Learning Control (ILC) comes to mind as a solution to previously stated problems. One of the ILC's advantages is robustness to uncertainty without the precise knowledge of the process model [1], [2]. ILC is also suitable for repetitive tasks, where each repetition has the same initial conditions. ILC is a highly modular control strategy that can be incorporated into existing control systems without changing them [3].

Extending ILC with fractional calculus theory, one obtains Fractional Order Iterative Learning Control (FOILC) [4]. Fractional calculus is a generalization of integer order calculus [5]. The main advantage of fractional order controllers is that they possess more degrees of freedom compared to their integer-order counterparts, implying better performance [6]. An increased number of control system parameters requires tuning for better system response. There is a considerable number of research involving tuning fractional order PID controllers in literature, for example [7], [8], but the FOILC controllers lack the proper tuning procedure. The research in [9] deals with the problem of tuning FOILC control parameters on a linearized robot with no uncertainty. The main motivation for this research is to find an easy, computationally efficient, and performance-improving solution to tuning FOILC parameters. This research also aimed to determine the proposed controller robustness to various percentages of parametric uncertainties of the proposed tuned control system. The Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) is our algorithm of choice for FOILC parameter tuning.

This paper consists of the following sections: Section II

describes the robot structure and the equations of motion are derived; Section III consists of the controller design description divided into subsections describing Inverse Dynamics, Fractional Order Iterative Learning Controller, and tuning procedure of the FOILC control parameters using PSO; Section IV showcases the simulation results of the previously presented controller.

2. ROBOT DYNAMICS DERIVATION

2.1. NeuroArm robot mechanical structure

The controller design presented in this paper is tested on the model of the NeuroArm robotic system with seven degrees of freedom (DOF) from the Laboratory of Applied Mechanics at the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering in Belgrade, Figure 1. The NeuroArm is a serial robot where the first three joints position the end-effector, while the following three joints orientate the end-effector. The 7th DOF is related to the gripper action. The mechanical structure of the NeuroArm robot is presented in Figure 2. In this contribution, we will only consider the 3-DOF positioning part of the NeuroArm kinematic chain.

Figure 1. Robotic system NeuroArm

2.2. Equations of motion

The dynamic behavior of the robotic system is described with the equations of motion (1), which are herein derived using the Rodriguez approach [10]:

$$\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{q})\ddot{\mathbf{q}} + \mathbf{C}(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}})\dot{\mathbf{q}} = \mathbf{Q}^a + \mathbf{Q}^g(\mathbf{q}), \quad (1)$$

where term $\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{q})$ is $n \times n$ inertia matrix, term $\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}})\dot{\mathbf{q}}$ is a $n \times 1$ Coriolis and centrifugal forces vector, term $\mathbf{Q}^g(\mathbf{q})$ is a $n \times 1$ vector of generalized forces due to gravity, and terms $\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}}$ are $n \times 1$ vectors of generalized coordinates $q_j, \dot{q}_j, j=1, \dots, n$ representing joint positions and speeds, respectively. Term \mathbf{Q}^a is $m \times 1$ vector of joint actuation torques, where m is a number of actuated joints. In this case $m=n=3$ since every joint of the robot has an independent source of actuation and only the first three DOFs of the NeuroArm are considered. The required data for deriving the equations of motion for the NeuroArm

presented in Figure 2. is listed in appendix in Table A.1.

Due to the complexity and inability to perfectly measure and estimate the parameters of the real-world robot, a level of uncertainty is present.

Figure 2. Mechanical structure of the NeuroArm

Hence, to better describe the impact of uncertainty on the behaviour of the robotic system and to test the proposed controller's performance, equations of motion (1) can be reformulated as:

$$(\mathbf{A}_N + \Delta\mathbf{A})\ddot{\mathbf{q}} + (\mathbf{C}_N + \Delta\mathbf{C})\dot{\mathbf{q}} - (\mathbf{Q}_N^g + \Delta\mathbf{Q}^g) = \mathbf{Q}^a, \quad (2)$$

where matrices $\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{q})$, $\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}})$ and vector $\mathbf{Q}^g(\mathbf{q})$ are split into nominal parts $\mathbf{A}_N(\mathbf{q})$, $\mathbf{C}_N(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}})$ and $\mathbf{Q}_N^g(\mathbf{q})$ and uncertain parts $\Delta\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{q})$, $\Delta\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{q})$ and $\Delta\mathbf{Q}^g(\mathbf{q})$. The dependence of matrices $\mathbf{A}_N(\mathbf{q})$, $\mathbf{C}_N(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}})$, $\Delta\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{q})$, $\Delta\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{q})$ and vectors $\mathbf{Q}_N^g(\mathbf{q})$, $\Delta\mathbf{Q}^g(\mathbf{q})$ on generalized coordinates vectors \mathbf{q} and $\dot{\mathbf{q}}$ will be omitted forward on.

3. CONTROL SYSTEM DESIGN

3.1. Solution to Inverse Dynamics problem

Robotic systems are coupled nonlinear, time-varying, Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO) systems, and as such, to successfully tackle the nonlinear dynamic coupling effects, a nonlinear control strategy is recommended. One of the most effective model-based nonlinear control strategies is Inverse Dynamics Control

(also known as Feedback linearization) [11], [12], [13]. Inverse Dynamics is a model-based control method. Inverse Dynamics, in theory, is the exact linearization of the system. Real-world robotic systems will always have some level of uncertainty, whether in mass or any other parameter, meaning that the exact linearization based on the derived model isn't achievable in practice. Considering the previous statement, the Inverse Dynamics accounts only for the nominal (known) part of the robot dynamics, and the vector of actuation torques \mathbf{Q}^a can be chosen such that it depends on those nominal parts:

$$\mathbf{Q}^a = \mathbf{A}_N \mathbf{u} + \mathbf{C}_N \dot{\mathbf{q}} - \mathbf{Q}_N^a, \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{u} is a new input vector. Substituting (3) in (2), alternative form of the equations of motions is obtained:

$$\ddot{\mathbf{q}} = \mathbf{A}^{-1} \mathbf{A}_N \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{A}^{-1} (\Delta \mathbf{C} \dot{\mathbf{q}} - \Delta \mathbf{Q}^a). \quad (4)$$

3.2. Fractional order iterative learning controller

Continuing from (4), a new control input vector \mathbf{u} is to be chosen to stabilize the system and tackle the uncertain parts of the robot dynamics model. Iterative learning controllers have been proven successful in precise trajectory tracking and compensating for parametric uncertainties and deterministic disturbances [1]. Here, the FOILC PD $^\alpha$ -type controller is considered to improve trajectory tracking and ensure system robustness to uncertainties compared to integer order. The proposed linear control law \mathbf{u} is divided into the feedback and feedforward part, where the feedback part is a classical PD controller, and the feedforward part is previously mentioned FOILC. The control input vector \mathbf{u} is defined by the following equations:

$$\mathbf{u}_i = \mathbf{u}_i^{fb} + \mathbf{u}_i^{ff}, \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{u}_i^{fb} = \mathbf{K}_P \mathbf{e}_i + \mathbf{K}_D \dot{\mathbf{e}}_i, \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{u}_i^{ff} = \mathbf{Q}_f [\mathbf{u}_{i-1} + \mathbf{K}_P^{ff} \mathbf{e}_{i-1} + \mathbf{K}_D^{ff} D_{CL}^{\alpha_j} (\mathbf{e}_{i-1})], \quad (7)$$

where i is the iteration index, j is the joint index, $\mathbf{e}_i = \mathbf{q}_d - \mathbf{q}_i$ is $n \times 1$ vector of position errors, $\dot{\mathbf{e}}_i = \dot{\mathbf{q}}_d - \dot{\mathbf{q}}_i$ is the $n \times 1$ vector of velocity errors, \mathbf{K}_P , \mathbf{K}_D are feedback gains, \mathbf{K}_P^{ff} , \mathbf{K}_D^{ff} are feedforward learning gains, $D_{CL}^{\alpha_j}$ is the fractional derivative operator of the order α_j according to the Grunwald-Letnikov definition, and \mathbf{Q}_f is a zero-phase low-pass filter added to suppress learning of the undesired frequencies [14]. The overview of the proposed controller structure is displayed in Figure A.1 in appendix.

3.3. Tuning procedure using Particle Swarm Optimization

Introducing fractional derivative and integral operators in control laws gives more degrees of freedom to the controllers, implying that better performance can be

achieved. In [15], it is shown that increasing the fractional order α value of the derivative operator leads to improved error convergence. Based on previous observations, it is only natural that the fractional order values are suitable for tuning after each iteration. Besides α , there are learning gains \mathbf{K}_P^{ff} and \mathbf{K}_D^{ff} in the FOILC control law (7) that influence the system output and should be subject to the tuning procedure.

The PID-type ILC control laws like (7) don't have as well-established tuning procedures as classical PID controllers [16]. Hence, this research chooses the PSO algorithm as a simple solution to the FOILC control parameters tuning problem. Particle Swarm Optimization is a nature-inspired optimization algorithm that draws inspiration from the social behavior of organisms such as birds and fish. Introduced in [17], PSO has gained popularity as a powerful heuristic optimization technique for solving complex optimization problems. Since its beginnings, the PSO algorithm has undergone significant changes and improvements. The variation of the PSO algorithm used in this research can be found in [18], and PSO parameters are listed in Table 1. Most of the parameters in Table 1 are set by trial and error. The tuning procedure is carried out after each iteration i , and tuned variables α , \mathbf{K}_P^{ff} and \mathbf{K}_D^{ff} are used in the next iteration $i+1$. The objective function for the PSO algorithm to minimize is adopted in the following form:

$$J = P + \sum_{t=0}^T t e_i^T e_i T, \quad (8)$$

where T is the duration of one iteration, $\mathbf{e}_i(t) = \mathbf{q}_d(t) - \mathbf{q}_i(t)$ is the position error and P is a penalty value that is added to the objective function according to the following cases:

$$P = \begin{cases} 0, & 0 < \alpha_j \leq 2 \wedge \mathbf{K}_P^{ff}, \mathbf{K}_D^{ff} > 0 \\ 1000, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad (9)$$

The value P penalizes particles, which can cause unstable behavior, and such particles are eliminated from the search process by adding additional costs to them. The described control system with PSO tuning is given in appendix in Figure A.1.

Table 1. Parameters for the PSO algorithm.

Variable	Value
Population number	50
Iteration number	10
Initial value of the individual-best acceleration factor	2.5
Final value of the individual-best acceleration factor	0.5
Initial value of the global-best acceleration factor	0.5
Final value of the global-best acceleration factor	2.5
Initial value of the inertia factor	0.9

Final value of the inertia factor	0.4
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4. SIMULATION RESULTS

The simulation is carried out in Matlab 2022a (version 9.12) and Simulink (version 10.5) using the Runge-Kutta solver (ode4) for ordinary differential equations with fixed-step $T_s = 0.001s$. The desired trajectories are defined in joint space as cubic polynomials:

$$q_1^d = -0.25 t^3 + 0.75 t^2 \tag{10}$$

$$q_2^d = -0.15 t^3 + 0.45 t^2 \tag{11}$$

$$q_3^d = -0.075 t^3 + 0.225 t^2 \tag{12}$$

Due to the servo motors saturation limits, feedback gains KP and KD are limited to the following value ranges:

$$K_P \in (0,10], K_D \in (0,5]. \tag{13}$$

In this simulation, feedback gains are tuned by trial and error:

$$K_P = \text{diag}(10,10,10), K_D = (5,5,5). \tag{14}$$

The quality of the proposed fractional order iterative learning controller is measured using Maximum Absolute Error (MAE). For each joint, the MAE is calculated per iteration. The system performance is evaluated based on the convergence of the MAE over the iteration axis. Number of iterations is set to $i_{max} = 10$. Table 2., 3., and 4. shows optimized learning gains and fractional order values at the 10th iteration. The proposed controller is compared to the classical integer order ILC controller, and the performance improvement can be seen from Figure 3.

Table 2. Results of the tuning procedure for $\Delta m = 0.1m_N$.

Joint j	α_j	$K_P^{\alpha_j}$	$K_D^{\alpha_j}$	J
1	1.05	5.17	0.61	$1.3 \cdot 10^{-8}$
2	0.72	3.48	1.77	
3	1.47	7.18	1.33	

Table 3. Results of the tuning procedure for $\Delta m = 0.2m_N$.

Joint j	α_j	$K_P^{\alpha_j}$	$K_D^{\alpha_j}$	J
1	1.36	0.96	0.04	$9.4 \cdot 10^{-8}$
2	1.7	0.6	2.79	
3	0.06	5.05	1.9	

Table 4. Results of the tuning procedure for $\Delta m = 0.3m_N$.

Joint j	α_j	$K_P^{\alpha_j}$	$K_D^{\alpha_j}$	J
1	1.8	7.28	1.17	$3.9 \cdot 10^{-7}$
2	0.95	0.58	0.25	
3	2	2.35	0.36	

Figure 4. shows a comparison of MAE convergence for each joint for different levels of mass uncertainties. The proposed FOILC with PSO tuning shows improved convergence in comparison to integer order ILC, and PSO-FOILC achieves satisfactory MAE convergence for different percentages of mass and inertial uncertainties.

Figure 3. Comparison of maximum absolute error between integer order ILC and PSO tuned fractional order ILC for $\Delta m = 0.1m_N$.

Figure 4. Maximum absolute error for different mass uncertainties per joint.

5. CONCLUSION

This paper investigated the performance of a PSO-tuned FOILC controller for a robotic system with parametric uncertainty. The key point is using a metaheuristic optimization algorithm PSO to tune FOILC parameters based on a defined objective function. Comparing PSO-FOILC with classical integer order ILC simulation results, it may be concluded that the former controller performed better. The tests with various percentages of mass uncertainty showed that PSO-FOILC successfully converges within ten iterations. The future prospect is to include feedback controller gains in the optimization process and friction in the robot model.

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APPENDIX A.

Figure A.1. Control system block diagram with PSO tuning.

Table A.1. Neuroarm robot manipulator parameters.

Joint j	1	2	3
\mathbf{e}_j^θ	$[0 \ 0 \ 1]^T$	$[-1 \ 0 \ 0]^T$	$[-1 \ 0 \ 0]^T$
\mathbf{p}_j^θ	$[0.023 \ -0.033 \ -0.17]^T$	$[0.051 \ -0.013 \ -0.223]^T$	$[0.029 \ -0.179 \ 0.047]^T$
\mathbf{p}_{ff}^θ	$[0 \ 0 \ 0.47]^T$	$[0 \ 0 \ 0.235]^T$	$[0 \ 0.3 \ 0]^T$
m_j	3.36	2.25	1.67
\mathbf{J}_c^θ	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.042 & 0.003 & 0.002 \\ 0.003 & 0.049 & 0.003 \\ 0.002 & -0.003 & 0.047 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.034 & -0.002 & -0.009 \\ -0.002 & 0.045 & 0.003 \\ -0.009 & -0.046 & 0.016 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.039 & -0.001 & -0.0002 \\ -0.001 & 0.01 & 0.002 \\ -0.0002 & 0.002 & 0.004 \end{bmatrix}$